

STAGES OF FORMATION OF ECO-LITERACY IN THE PROCESS OF MODERNIZATION OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION AND ITS PEDAGOGICAL DESCRIPTION

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of eco-literacy in students in the process of modernization of environmental education, pedagogical-psychological features of modernization of environmental education, the corrective effect of eco-creativity, eco-responsibility, eco-literacy competencies in students between nature and human relations studied. Modern pedagogical approaches to the modernization of environmental education are also analyzed.

Key words: ecology, biosphere, formation of eco-literacy, environment, national values, healthy lifestyle, ecological dialogue, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, value, value approach, national, historical, technological.

INTRODUCTION. Today, the scope of scientific research aimed at the formation of eco-literacy is considered based on a one-sided approach. According to the head of our state: "Currently, the material and technical base of these scientific institutions does not allow to carry out modern researches. It is also true that research is still carried out in old fashioned ways. We must also admit that there is a lack of personnel who have thoroughly mastered the achievements of modern science in the field." In our opinion, it is necessary to carry out research on ecology today, taking into account socio-pedagogical, territorial-geographical, ethnographic-mental characteristics, based on an innovative approach and serving the atmosphere of the living soul. Scientific literature created by scientists and specialists of our country serves as a tool that helps the formation and development of ecological culture in every person.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical foundations of ecological education are expressed in the research works of Academician I.D. Zverev, A.N. Zakhlebniy, the content, methodology, form, and tools of ecological education in teaching natural sciences by E.O. Turdigulov. The biological direction of ecological education was studied by I. T. Suravegina, as well as socio-philosophical aspects by Y. Shodimetov, B. Ziyomukhamedov. In the researches of L.T.Shonosirova, G.O.Komilova, environmental education of preschool children, and in the researches of M.A.Yuldashev, M.M.Abdullayeva, M.B.Rahimkulova, G.Sultonova, N.Ashurova, issues of environmental knowledge in primary education were studied.

Abroad, scientists R.G. Barker, W.R. Catton, D.D. Chiras, R.E. Dunlap, the content and essence, structure of environmental education; the issues of creating eco-literacy in students were mentioned in the scientific research of D.H. Meadows, D. L. Meadows, J. Randers, A. W. Wiecker, Ch. M. Geesteranus, J. C. Smith, L. F. Schmore, A. J. Suvan, O. D. Duncan, S. Foresman, and U. Halbach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Through ecological education and upbringing, people, including young people, acquire knowledge about Mother Nature, the environment, the universe, natural environment and processes, and scientific and theoretical worldviews about human relationships. Therefore, in the development of environmental education and training, special attention should be paid to ensure the harmony of corporate-pedagogical, motivational, environmental attachment, reflexivity, pedagogical-psychological abilities of students with rationality. Especially in this regard, the empirical analysis of the levels of internal and external manifestations of ecological knowledge is of great importance for the improvement of acocid. This means that the natural-geographical features of their homeland, ecosystems and their emergence, evolutionary development, anthropogenic changes, laws of distribution in large-scale situations, resulting features, wealth, condition, future prospects, national, nature and society relations on a regional and global scale, practical environmental skills and competences, understanding the problems related to the protection of the Earth's surface environment, rational use of its resources and the restoration of damaged natural complexes and making the right decisions to find their solutions has a positive effect on the improvement of competence. Also, depending on the chosen professions, the system of environmental education is formed and developed. In general, ecology is a single system of science → education → practice. Therefore, the algorithmic stages of improving environmental education for students should be improved from simple to complex, consistency and continuity, taking into account the age, physical capabilities and psychological characteristics of students, on the basis of the purposeful systematization of the relationship of theoretical and practical knowledge. This should be the fundamental scientific-theoretical basis of environmental education and training.

Eco-literacy is the level of motivation to be able to use the opportunities of a person with high ecological spirituality and enlightenment in his life, including work. That is, the creation of the conditions for feeling how necessary environmental consciousness and culture are in life and enjoying its positive results within certain administrative management units or economic sectors. It is manifested in the environmental concept, policy, legislation, action program and work plans of the state, society and corporate associations, priority research directions, personnel training and their practical implementation.

The essence of ecological education and practice is reflected in its three-dimensional research, teaching and implementation. That is, protection of ecosystems (natural and anthropogenically changed), rational use of natural resources of ecosystems, restoration of damaged ecosystems. Ecology is to ensure the unity of environmental education, upbringing and practice to achieve the safety of ecosystems that ensure the sustainable development of current and future generations. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to perform the following environmental tasks in educational processes:

- development of universally recognized scientific-theoretical foundations of ecology, assessment of its history, current state and future prospects in the context of various ecosystems;
- development of an ecological concept and program of actions;
- adoption of tactical and strategic environmental development plans;
- revision of personnel training system for ecology and environmental protection;
- creation of a mechanism for comprehensive analysis of the environmental legislation base and its connection with practice;

-implementation of the mandatory principle of national environmental education;

- encourages solving issues such as revising environmental education in accordance with the rules of sustainable development.

Also, environmental security is an integral part of national security, and it differs from other security factors in its hidden nature. Therefore, imparting ecological knowledge and concepts in the national education system is one of the most urgent problems of our time. Environmental education is carried out in pre-school educational institutions, schools, secondary vocational technical schools and higher educational institutions and neighborhoods.

That is why it is appropriate to start imparting environmental knowledge and concepts according to educational stages from preschool age.

Educating children of pre-school age with high moral qualities, improving their national spirituality, respect for our rich cultural heritage, historical traditions, universal human values, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideals of independence is the key to all the reforms implemented in our country. is a factor.

By introducing children of preschool age to the environment, it is possible for them to acquire comprehensive knowledge, develop mental processes, develop their abilities, form their worldview, acquire moral qualities, and acquire positive behavioral habits. Concepts about the environment surrounding the child: love for the Motherland, introducing them to our history and the great scholars of the East, their lives and works, and enriching their knowledge about famous generals, holidays, and folk art are of great importance.

In the "First Step" educational program, developed on the basis of "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age", the "Development of the cognitive process" field in the field of "Development of the cognitive process" in the formation of the understanding of children of different age groups about the world includes the following knowledge on the competences of a 6-7-year-old child. It is intended to acquire:

- observation and research of events in the environment;
- to show a careful and caring attitude towards the environment.

Mental and aesthetic attitudes towards nature are closely related to the content of the knowledge acquired by the child. The knowledge related to the content of introduction to nature guides children's activities in nature and their self-control, discipline and directs them towards the goal. Knowledge of the laws of nature, which are sufficiently accessible to children's perception, occupies a special place in the formation of an attitude towards nature. The development of the attitude towards nature (life situation such as training, excursion, walk) is closely related to the organization of the pedagogical process based on the child's spiritual and positive spiritual experiences. At this stage, special attention should be paid to the fact that corporate-pedagogical, motivational, adaptation to the environment, reflexivity, pedagogical-psychological factors form the basis of environmental education.

Providing students with theoretical knowledge of ecology from primary grades is one of the main priority tasks of forming an ecological worldview in the system of natural sciences. As long as the ecological worldview does not become an ecological ethical criterion, the distance between man and nature will continue to widen. That is why it is important to pay special attention to students' understanding of living nature through visual means. Also, in Uzbekistan, taking into account the experience of foreign countries, we can see that the

topics of natural sciences intended for elementary school students are adapted to foreign standards. In particular, learning technologies are widely used to divide the world into animate and inanimate nature, to learn about the world through observation. It is desirable to inculcate the development processes of the world of plants, their types, the conditions under which they grow and the characteristics of flexibility, and the values of caring for the world of plants.

In the "Journey to the Animal World" section for primary classes, fish living on land and in water are classified separately. Animal development processes are analyzed. Also, it is necessary to theoretically explain weather and natural phenomena, their occurrence, seasons and their differences, weather variations in seasons. To provide students with information about natural landscapes, forests, deserts, deserts and oceans through the theme of forests, and through the theme of earth and space, to learn about the earth, sun, moon and through his classification, the movement of celestial bodies, heat, light, and sound, his attitude toward nature begins to change through his ability to differentiate between the sources of light, heat, and sound in the room and in nature. In the upbringing of a child, the environment in which he lives, the activities of the people play a major role, and in this area, the family and school conditions are also of special importance.

Ecological education is also the main part of education, it has a strong influence on the child's behavior and calls on parents to educate them from childhood. Environmental education and general education are a whole process related to each other.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, ensuring environmental security at the state level by developing a strategy of national environmental education and upbringing requires the implementation of individual educational stages of ecologically enlightened and spiritual, i.e. ecologically cultured, individuals in society.

References:

1. Абдуллаев М. ва бошқалар. Маданиятшунослик асослари. Т., 2006.
2. Жабборов И. Ўзбек халқи этнографияси -Т.: "Ўқитувчи", 1994.-320 б.
3. Кулешова М.Е., Мазуров Ю.Л. Экологические функции как основа выявления ценности территорий // Уникальные территории в природном и культурном наследии регионов. М.: РНИИ культурного и природного наследия, 1994.
4. Соболев Н.А. Региональная стратегия территориальной охраны природы // Критерии и методы формирования экологической сети природных территорий. Вып. 1. – 2-е изд. – М.: Центр охраны дикой природы СоЭС, 1999.
5. <http://book.inf.uz>